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AN OUTLINE TO OPTIMIZE THE QUALITY ASSURANCE AND ROLE OF THE EXAMINATION COMMITTEES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Since the adjustments in the Dutch Law on Higher Education and Research Act in 2010, the Dutch universities have initiated an overall operation to optimize the mechanisms to monitor the quality assurance of examinations and the regulations. At the Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) in the Netherlands, the Examination Committees (EC) have modified their positions accordingly. The ECs in all Engineering study program at the TU/e operate in an independent and proactive manner and hold expertise in a number of fields such as legal, quality assurance, research and statistical analysis on quality of exams, among others.

Within this legal framework of changes the Examination Committee at the departments has taken an even more important role in monitoring and safeguarding the procedures. To strengthen the position of the Examination Committee new tasks and roles have been carefully defined. The EC is now to determine objectively whether the student meets the end qualifications of the study program and curriculum; to establish procedures and regulations within the Education and Examinations Framework of the department regarding the assessment and determining the results of examinations; to safeguard the quality of the organization and examination procedures, including Bachelor and Master thesis; and to take measures against fraud, among others.

In this paper, we will present a case on how the Applied Physics (AP) department has made changes regarding the quality of assessment specifically, and in general in the organization of the Examination Committee to accommodate the new demands by the law. We will outline how the AP Examination Committee has given form to its role to pay attention to assure the quality of examinations and assessment. In addition, we will explain with examples the methods used to research the quality of examinations.

Conference Key Areas: Quality assurance and accreditation; Curriculum development; Skills and engineering education